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Exploring the Relationship between Effective Teaching and Learning Outcomes in EFL Contexts: A Critical Perspective

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ABSTRACT

This research was aimed to find out the effectiveness of teaching methods that could have positive impact on EFL students' learning and institutional well being. The study also investigated students' perceptions towards teaching methods to see 'to what extent teaching methods used by EFL teachers are useful and to what extent teaching methods are effective. The explored what ought to take effective measures to enhance teaching efficiency that could cause better outcomes. Several educationists have produced and found various teaching methods and behaviors of teachers that may have influence on students' achievements in the process of learning. This study found some of the most important methods like lecture, discussion, the combination of lecture and discussion, role play and case studies through critical appraisal and were presented to examine teachers and students' efficiency regardless of different educators favor different methods. Finally, to evaluate the effectiveness of various teaching methods, students' perceptions were collected in order to find out the effectiveness of teachers' approaches and methods on students' learning English as foreign language.

KEYWORDS: EFL teachers, teaching methods, EFL students, students' achievements, EFL learning.

Introduction

Teaching in the absence of learning is just talking. There is a relationship between what the teacher taught to their students and what students gained through his teaching. Thus the learning and progress is based on the teacher's effectiveness. Now a day's students become more expert in guessing that a method which an instructor is using in a class is either a best method or he merely used it for his own comfort (Doyle.T.(n.d). "Research indicates that students are the most qualified sources to report on the extent to which the learning experience was productive, informative, satisfying, or worthwhile. While opinions on these matters are not direct measures of instructor or course effectiveness, they are legitimate indicators of student satisfaction, and there is substantial research linking student satisfaction to effective teaching (Franklin, 2001)." It is seen that teachers contains a vast amount of knowledge and his major role is to convey the information of his abilities and subject to their learners. Thus the main purpose of effective teaching would to impart all the knowledge about a specific topic to their students. To assess the capabilities of others the act of a teacher is a private experience during the transmission of knowledge. The role of teacher during the

transformation of knowledge to their students is much like a dramatic actor who attempts to gain the concentration of their spectators. He wants to know the effect of his communication upon his students mentally and instinctively. Berliner (2005) states that "effective teaching is about reaching achievement goals; it is about students learning what they are supposed to in a particular context, grade or subject" (p. 207). According to Braskamp and Ory, (1994, p. 40) effective teaching is the "creation of situations in which appropriate learning occurs; shaping those situations is what successful teachers have learned to do effectively".

Views upon the Effectiveness and Behavior of Teacher:

To guide an effective teacher Quina (1989, p. 5) presented some principles that are as follows. She said that in the process of learning the facilities should be involved and both the teacher and students should have shared experience between them. She said that a good teacher is one who transfers all his skills and knowledge to his/her learners. He examine the contents of material and after examining he transfer the information of it to the learners. Furthermore, he enables his students to think critically and explore the outer word and the features of their life. He motivates, encourage and help the students in finding the knowledge within them.

According to Phipps (1988, p. 145) "good teaching or effective teaching is the direction of the leaning process in which the desirable changes of a relatively permanent nature are brought about within the learner as a result of the instruction."

An educationalist Murray (1991) makes a research on the behavior of effective teacher, to examine the effectiveness of teaching. He stated that to motivate and train the student the clarity and enthusiasm are necessary and sufficient conditions. He argued that most of the teachers conduct their classes in lecture style. A bold statement was formulated by him that, "classroom teaching behaviors, at least in the enthusiasm and clarity domains, appear to be causal antecedents (rather than mere correlates) of various instructional outcome measures" (p. 161). Outside the classroom the teacher cannot control the students but his own behavior and academic decisions are under his control that can also have greater impact upon the learning of students. According to Williams and Burden (1997) "one of the many aspects that teachers bring to the teaching-learning process is a view of what education is all about, and this belief, whether implicit or explicit, will influence their actions in the classroom" (pp. 48-49). They further hold that "learners' perceptions and interpretations have been found to have the greatest influence on achievement" (p. 98).

Perception of Students to Teaching Effectiveness:

Hill, Lomas, & MacGregor, (2003) holds that, according to the perception of students in higher education sectors it is often seen that the attitude and behavior of a teacher counts a lot. The impact of a good teacher on their students considered strong enough. Thus the education sectors and institutions should give attention to their students that what they need and what they want (Joseph, Yakhou, & Stone, 2005). The student's perception is regarded more valuable in evaluating and improving the teachings of a teacher. Many characteristics of effective teacher are normally advance according to student's perception. For a charismatic teacher all of these characteristics are crucial. A significant quality of a good teacher is that he must have knowledge (Lammers & Murphy, 2002) . Koehler & Mishra, (2009) stated that, the practice of teaching is difficult to a large extent because in it various types of particular knowledge and its amalgamation include. Voss & Gruber, (2006) believed that, a good teacher is one who have full command on their subject and convey it to their students in a very clear and distinct manner. Chou (1997) stated that, as teachers are role

models for students, so they should give their special treatment to the performance of the student's self and should show suitable behavior to them which reflect moral values.

Some of the researchers show that effective teachers have a large amount of knowledge and skills when they use their methods of teaching and then they can make lessons interesting (Stronge, 2002). Thus the teachers who created pleasant and peaceful environment in the classroom were considered the favorite teachers of the students and they remember them as a good teacher. And a teacher is regard as charismatic when all the traits like excellent methods of teaching, being educated and good sense of humor works together with harmony.

There are also some suggestions for an effective teacher that he should know how to deliver lecture and what would students gain from it. Chou (1997) stated that, a teacher should teach the students what he knows, not what he does not know. Students favor the humorous side of teacher during the lecture according to Minchew, Neumann . Another suggestion is that a teacher should give priority to the methods of teaching and from the variety of methods he should choose the most appropriate methods (Voss & Gruber, 2006). Carkhuff (1981) stated that effective teaching helps in promoting the emotional, intellectual, physical and social development of the learners. Every student's background and abilities are different. Thus a good teaching not only contains effectiveness but it fulfills the needs of the learners. Furthermore Joyce (1986) and Weil (1995) hold that "students react differently to different teaching methods, and that the selection of the proper method is critical to the learning style of those being served by the instruction" (p. 260).

Use of Various Teaching Methods:

The term method means the process or procedures through which a teacher is chosen to help the learners in the process of learning. There are many perplexing conceptions of the methods of teaching. In defining the methods of teaching various educators or writers are contradict with each other because of the plentiful concepts of the methods. According to the intellectual approach of the students, teacher use different methods of teaching for their better understanding. Using student learning outcomes as the criteria for effectiveness, several commonly-used teaching methods (lecture, lecture/discussion combination, role play, brainstorming, case study,) were applied and evaluated in a class setting. In addition, information on student opinions of the teaching methods was gathered and critically analyzed those methods. Some of the most important methods of teaching and many suggestions to advance these methods are as follows:

- 1. Lecture:** A lecture is a linguistic presentation which is given to the students by their teacher. In spite of all the ultra modern technologies in the process of teaching the method of lecture is still famous among students and also perusing at higher level. This method is not time consuming but it is a backbone of all the education system and through this method teacher have full control on the material which he delivered to the students. According to Benson, L., Schroeder, P., Lantz, C., and Bird, M, students give their much attention to that material which was given by lecture rather than the books or handouts. The meaning of lecture is not that a teacher should stand in front of the class and delivered all the material that he knows. In "Common Teaching Methods" McCarthy, P. (1992) holds that the strong points of a lecture is that it is based on facts, logic, critical analysis that inspire the audiences at a great level and provokes in them the sense of judgment. It is discovered by many educationalist that the student consider the lecture scheme as the most excellent method. Some of the new ideas are created through this method and among students it enhances the factor of creativity. Through this method teacher gain command on his subject and can answer all the

questions that were raised by his students. Thus lecture should be exhilarating. In this method the information must be conveyed to the students by the use of examples so that it can store in their minds. The questions should be used by teacher during the lecture to check that either the students are attentive in the class or not. The process of learning should make interesting by the use of charts, white or black boards, graphs and filmstrips. To improve the method of lecture teacher ought to know the views of students

2. Discussion:

Among the pupil and teacher it is a lexical communication of ideas. Before the discussion the student should know how to the relevant topic to attain positive outcomes during discussion. According to Kochhar (2000, p.347), during discussion, arguments, explanations and critical analysis are appropriate. The discussion among students provokes the confidence among them and learning becomes more remarkable. In this method student so not trust on cramming and the sense of judgment and method of creativity arises among them. In organizing the method of discussion and to fix the attention of the students to the topic of discussion teacher should spend much time. To arrive at conclusion there must be a time limit. Before starting, the teacher should elaborate the history of the topic which is going to discuss and encourage students for participating in it without any hesitation. To give direction to the topic, the portion of questions should be included by teachers. To promote the process of discussion the environment of the class should peaceful. Teacher should give confidence to the students to listen others statement and be able to express their own point of view. To avoid the sense of discrimination the teacher should pay attention to the suggestions of all students and should not be favoritism among students.

3. Role Play:

It is a technique that allows students to explore realistic situations by the interaction to their professors. Through this method the arrangement of behaviors, character and beliefs comes into existence. To a large extent this technique established the applicability by its learners (Singh, and Sudarshan, 2005, p 238, 239). Student can easily enjoy and memorize through this method.

The teacher should give brief description about the role play, to the students, before taking a start. Teacher should provide time to the students and not cut the role play clips. He must watch and to listen everything silently. He must advise the student that they should perform naturally not artificially. Teacher should pay attributes to the observers and say goodbye with cheerful remarks after the role play and asked them to give their comments.

4. Case Study:

The first and foremost use of case study was expended in the perspective of business and laws. But gradually it becomes famous in the engineering, arts and education process. The student solves their problem of real life and thinks critically in this method. It enables the students to interpret the specific issues and also enables him to provide the answers of the difficulties which were identified by him. Thus much of the time consumed in this method and the information which comes to us from this method is not satisfactory which leads us to improper outcomes. The students get fed up at last and they insist their teachers to provide them the exact answer. The teacher should study the case and after analyzing he should give solutions and elaborate some of the major issues faced by the student. The study of case must be precise and based on the issues of reality. It should uncover those

responses that are in opposition to each other. To prepare the report work of ant case the student should work in the form of group.

Analysis and critical appraisal of teaching methods and its effectiveness:

There are various other methods of teaching such as investigation, expository, question answer, encouragement, gaming and invention, that's why different questions are put forward by different educationalists. The old question is "which on should I use". This question open the ways to a new question: "which one should I use and for what purpose"? Various methods of teachings are exposed to the students and they distinguish that which methods are effective and have specific outcomes (Henson, 1988, p.89). According to Kassem (1992, p. 45), teaching methods are those in which a teacher involves the students in the class activities and share that experience of learning with other learners. A good teacher must have manipulate the learners when he/she used various styles of teachings, works as a friend with them, make the area of learning peaceful and organize his/her lesson plans. These different strategies of teaching are linked with the achievement of students learning, according to various studies. It is observed that to make the process of learning much adequate and useful the different types of learning aids works as tools to simplify the complex ideas and to make the connection of new and old ideas (Yelon, 1996, p. 131).

Henson (1988, p. 9), stated that to help the students in the process of learning should be the real goal of a good teacher. In preparing a lesson three roles should followed by a teacher, First role involve "identify some of the important ideas or concepts that will be developed in the unit and to explain the importance of this material to the students." The second is to give students an opportunity to include areas within the unit that they think should be studied", the third and last is that in which teachers need to help in selecting activities necessary for developing an understanding of the unit (Henson, 1988, p. 17). Another educationalist Creswell (1990, p.16) categorized the teaching methodologies into individualized, interactive, teacher-centered and experimental. These are the integrative move towards learning. According to Yelon (1996) variations takes place in the classroom by the researchers during the lecture, to keep students attentive. He uses different techniques like demonstration, examples, and feedbacks for better explanation. Sometimes students understand the concept of a lesson by different examples which their teachers used and they discuss these concepts with each others. Sometimes a very short video or reading was given to the students during lecture and ask them to discuss it to your class fellows or write it precisely (p. 154). According to him, in the process of learning one of the most important techniques is using the aids. Following aids like film strips, transparencies, handouts and checklists are most valuable and as a result of this method the process of learning becomes much useful, adequate and satisfactory (p. 133). According to Carkhuff (1981)"some teachers emphasize the use of question and answer techniques while other uses a lot of programmed instruction. Still others utilize the lecture method in the classroom and using overhead projectors a great deal (p. 90)."Thus the reality is that every teacher has their own methods of teaching which they use in the class. Fosnot (1989) argued that there are different views of learning in which the traditional and constructivism are most famous. In the first view the lecture- base plan is involve, through which the lecture is conveyed to the students, on the other hand the second view involves the discussion in the learning process and students become active in this process. Through lecture students can be able to in recalling the truths but on the other hand an advanced understanding generates in the process of discussion. Another research shows that in the process of discussion, positive results like the qualities of guidance, membership and the level of confidence increases among students (Perkins & Saris, 2001).

Hunt, Haidet, Coverdale, and Richards (2003) focused on the method of team learning in evaluating the performance of students. They said that, in comparison to the lecture method, the team learning methods have positive aspects and more valuable. On the other hand Barnes & Blevins (2003) holds that the old and passive lecture base method of teaching is more valuable and superior to the discussion methods. While Morgan, Whorton, & Gunsalus (2000) stated that the combination of these two methods e.g. lecture and discussion have power over all other methods of teaching.

Thus there are various types of teachers and the methods of teachings. The actions of teachers are characterized by teacher's manner of teaching according to several researchers and their choices concerned with the methods of teaching. The process of teaching is multidimensional and it shed light on numerous aspects of a teacher which sometimes cannot be evaluated quantitatively (Boex, 2000).

Evaluation and perception of students:

It is common at higher level to evaluate the methods of teaching by students. The students of elementary level cannot make sophisticated judgments about the effectiveness and behavior of their teachers. There are various types of judgments that can make for the process of teaching. The level of sophistication develop among students when they grow old at this level they can make judgments that are valid.

The evaluations that are based on the performance will be different from those evaluations that are constructed by the students of different ages. Specific kind of teaching behavior like questioning, demonstrating were tracked by the observers to judge the performance-base evaluation. The words that were spoken by the teachers and the actions which he performs during the classroom were required full attention in the process of evaluation. The evaluations of students considered subjective because sometimes the evaluation which they make to check the behavior of teacher could influence their own behavior. Thus it can be said that the satisfaction of students about the behaviors and methods of teacher is necessary because they considered the "clients" of the educational institutes and the assessment which they make for teaching methodologies is much "authentic" than those peoples who observe from outside.

Student ' assessment of effective instructional behaviors and attitudes constitutes a large body of research on teaching in higher education. To identify the personality and qualities that are crucial for an effective teacher or the best teacher of the students' the information is collected from students. These studies are broader than the "process- product" studies in that they examine characteristics and behaviors exhibited by teachers both inside and outside the classroom. Overall, this research reveals that students and teachers share many perceptions of effective instruction, including teacher knowledge of subject and teacher organization and preparation for class. Perceptual differences between students and teachers do emerge from these studies. That is, the students are linked with the keenness and motivation of teachers which he makes in the lessons or in the material of course, on the other hand teachers are closely associated with the abilities of teachers who challenge his students intellectually and encourage the thinking curiosity among the students.

In most education sectors the evaluations of students about their teachers become a routine work. The recent study tells us that, the evaluation of students increase to check the effectiveness of their teachers all over the world (Hobson & Talbot, 2001; Hassan & Dzakiria, 2018). Many problems like the validity and progress of an evaluation mechanism, consistency of student's evaluations in assessing the teaching effectiveness arises during the student evaluation to check the effectiveness of teaching (Hofman & Kremer, 1980; Hassan & Dzakiria, 2020).

Student's stimulations and their perception about the effective teaching have checked which tells us that students personal opinions and active contribution in measuring the effectiveness of teaching is also crucial. The data which was given by the student about the teaching effectiveness will be useless if student will not willing. Thus the will of students counts a lot before measuring the teaching effectiveness. To make judgments in education sectors about effective teaching the questionnaires are specially designed to observe teaching behavior and style (Wright & O'Neil, 1992). The evaluation of students to assess the teaching effectiveness considered much important in many educational institutes (Kwan, 1999). There is an important relationship between the behaviors of students and their assessment towards teaching effectiveness (Marsh, 1984). Some of the important factors and the attitudes of students are analyzed by various studies. Two major functions (formative and summative) were put before to evaluate the effectiveness of teachers by their students. Some of the key responses were given by the students to their teachers so that they change their performance of teaching (Franklin, 1991).

The information about organizational assessments is considered a summative task. For the selection of teacher and contents by students, this task provides. But this function faced many disagreements and has not been adopted in many education sectors. To guide teachers, two general principles are presented by Ralph Tyler (1969, p. 65), in choosing educational skills. He said that (1) "for a given objective to be attained, a student must have experiences that give him an opportunity to practice the kind of behavior implied by the objective. For example, if one of the objectives is to develop skill in problem solving, this cannot be attained unless the learning experiences give the student ample opportunity to solve problems. (2) The learning experiences must be such that the student obtains satisfactions from carrying on the kind of behavior implied by the objectives". Moreover, Yelon (1996, p. 3) presented some principles that should apply by an effective teacher during the process of planning and educational skills. He said that a teacher should motivate the students about the learning of past, present and future. He should transfer the instruction to the students carefully so that they may be able to learn the relevant instruction at the next level. Teacher should aware of the needs and interests of students during learning. There should be an open communication between student and teacher in the classroom. He should help the students in learning and recalling the ideas which he delivered to them. To learn easily and quickly, a teacher should help the students by using various educational instruments and put them into practice in solving the problems, recalling and thinking. Teacher should make the environment of classroom pleasant so that students may easily learn, feel comfort and satisfaction with their teacher. Various tests and practices should be designed so that students and teachers can check their progress that what they learned and what they teach. Yelon advised teachers that they should considered these principles as the basics of teaching and should not copy the other teacher's style of teaching (Yelon, 1996; Hassan & Aziz, 2019).

Conclusion:

It is true that no nation can make progress unless an ideal guide will not among them. Teacher is a guide and acts like a ladder who remains at its place but helps others to go higher & higher. But for making progress the presence of an effective teacher should have primary importance. The behavior of teacher also counts a lot in all educational sectors. Students will gain what their teacher imparts to them. So teacher should have effective teaching skills that will help in enhancing the achievement of students. Various teaching methods were used to enhance the efficiency of students. The four methods of teaching were used in this article and after analyzing it is concluded that students gained knowledge from all these methods at some extent but educationalists have different point of views about teaching methods. Some says that lecture

method is good; other said that case study and project method are useful to attain the achievement. But the combination of both the lecture & discussion method is very famous among the educationalists and educational sectors. The method of case study and team project is not so much admired by various students. The evaluation of students should take place in measuring the effectiveness of teaching method. But no one should fully rely on the perception of the students because sometimes the element of liking and disliking arises among the student & teacher. To teach the learner's in efficient ways, teachers should provide some suggestions to the students to teach him about the various phases of life in front of him. And it is true that teachers cannot put into practice their lesson plans unless the managing and the motivation quality of teacher will be good. To advance the methods of teaching the teachers should know that which knowledge and skills are helpful. Thus by the use of various instruments and effective methodologies the learning of students can be raised and they can attain success.

REFERENCES:

- Barnes, D., & Blevins, D. (2003). An anecdotal comparison of three teaching methods used in the presentation of microeconomics. *Educational Research Quarterly*, 27(4), 41-60.
- Berliner, D. (2005). The near impossibility of testing for teacher quality. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 56(3), 207.
- Chou, T. D. (1997). *Teacher-student relationship in universities of Taiwan* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). National Chengchi University, Taipei, Taiwan.
- Doyle.T. (n.d.). *Evaluating Teachers Effectiveness*. Retrieved July 24, 2008, from ferris.edu/fctl/Teaching_and_Learning_Tips/.../EvalTeachEffec.htm
- Franklin, J. (2001). Interpreting the numbers: *Using a narrative to help others read student evaluations of your teaching accurately*. In K. G. Lewis (Ed.), *Techniques and strategies for interpreting student evaluations*. New Directions for Teaching and Learning, 87, 85-99. San Francisco, Ca: Jossey-Bass.
- Hassan, M.U & Aziz, A.A. (2019). [Impact of Motivational Achievement for EFL Learning Strategies: A Case of Pakistani University Students](#). *Al-Qalam*, 24 (1), 104-114.
- Hassan, M.U. Dzakiria, H. (2018). [Pakistani EFL Adult Learners' Beliefs towards Corrective Feedback in Cooperative Learning Strategy](#). *The Journal of Social Sciences Research*, 5, 749-753.
- Hassan, M.U. Dzakiria, H. (2020). [Investigating English teachers' organizational integrity and obligation in Pakistani universities](#). *Hamdard Islamicus*, 43 (1), 130-144.
- Henson, K. T. (1988). *Methods and Strategies for Teaching in Secondary and Middle Schools*. New York, NY: Longman. P; 89, 9, 17.
- Hill, Y., Lomas, L., & MacGregor, J. (2003). *Students' perceptions of quality in higher education*. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 11(1), 15-20.
- Hobson, S.M. & Talbot ,D.M. (2001). *Understanding student evaluations*, *College Teaching*,49 (1),pp. 26–31.
- Hofman, F.E. & Kremer,L. (1980). Attitudes toward higher education and course evaluation, *Journal of Educational Psychology*,72 (5), pp. 610–617.
- Joseph, M., Yakhou, M., & Stone, G. (2005). An educational institution's quest for service quality: *Customers' perspective*. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 13(1), 66-82.
- Kochkar, S.K. (2000). *Methods And Techniques Of Teaching*. New Delhi: Sterling. Singh, U.K and Sudarshan, K.N. (2005). *Teacher Education*. New Delhi: Discovery Publishing House. P.345, 347.

- Koehler, M. J., & Mishra, P. (2009). What is technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK)? *Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education*, 9(1), 60-70.
- Lammers, W. J., & Murphy, J. J. (2002). A profile of teaching techniques used in the university classroom: A descriptive profile of a US public university. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 3(1), 54-67.
- McCarthy, P. (1992). *Common Teaching Methods*. Retrieved from, <http://honolulu.hawaii.edu/intranet/committees/FacDevCom/guidebk/teachtip/comteach.htm>
- Morgan, R., Whorton, J., & Gunsalus, C. (2000). A comparison of short term and long term retention: Lecture combined with discussion versus cooperative learning. *Journal of Instructional Psychology*, 27(1), 53-58.
- Murray, H.G. (1991). Effective teaching behaviors in the college classroom. In J.C. Smart (Ed.), *Higher education: Handbook of theory and research* (vol. 6) (pp.135-172). New York: Agathon Press.
- Phipps, L. J., & Osborne, E. W. (1988). *Handbook on agricultural education in public schools*. Danville, IL: Interstate Printers & Publishers.
- Quina, J. (1989). *Effective Secondary Teaching: Going Beyond The Bell Curve*. New York, NY: Harper & Row Publishers. p; 5.
- Stronge, J. H. (2002). *Qualities of effective teachers*. Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Tyler, R. W. (1969). *Basic Principles of Curriculum and Instruction*. Chicago, IL: The University of Chicago Press. P; 65.
- Voss, R., & Gruber, T. (2006). The desired teaching qualities of lecturers in higher education: A means end analysis. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 14(3), 217-242.
- Wright, W.A. & O'Neil, M. C. (1992). Improving summative student ratings of instruction practice, *Journal of Staff, Program, and Organizational Development*, 10. pp. 75–85.
- Yelon, S. L. (1996). *Powerful Principles of Instruction*. Lancing, ML Longman Publishers. P; 3-4.
- Yining Chen & Leon, B. Hoshower. (2003). Student Evaluation of Teaching Effectiveness: An assessment of student perception and motivation, *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 28:1, and 71-73. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1080/02602930301683>